

RISK AND SECURITY PRACTICES: EXPERIENCES FROM THE E-LAND PROJECT

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The increasing availability of renewable energy resources and high expectations from end-users regarding energy dependability, has forced a re-thinking of how energy resources are connected and exploited in order to realize their full potential. New investments in electric infrastructures are costly and exploring alternative solutions (such as increasing the capacity of existing facilities in conjunction with new inexpensive technologies) are expected. The E-LAND project (elandh2020) takes a bottom-up approach analyzing the dynamics of the communities, where the actions are to take place, by addressing the needs of these communities instead of focusing only on the needs of the system operators. Regardless of the solutions created, the high expectations from end-users and society at large still applies. In this paper we address several good practices followed during the risk assessment performed for both the project and designed software products to ensure that the concept, the solution and the application developed in the E-LAND project are both safe and secure, and thereby reliable (CCPS, 2008) (MIL-STD-882E, 2012). On the project side, a monthly update by each risk owner of the project risk register is helping the stakeholders to stay aware of the risk and simplify how mitigations shall be included in the management project and the project's organization. On the technical part, the first requirements for the product were based on systems suppliers and developers' needs, here the risk analysis process identified that privacy and security measures were missing with regards to reliability. This paper describes the assumptions on how this could happen, how the risk analysis was performed and communicated and how the risk analysis provided input to the project to mitigate these risks prior to development. This example indicates that the awareness and the concerns on privacy and cyber security risks might be underrated or unclear when the requirements are predominately motivated by functionality alone and not from an overall focus on all aspects in the project. This example is discussed in further detail and provide the suggested mitigations to deal with safety, security and privacy for the project (GDPR, 2016/679). We report on how the extended safety and security focus has been received in the project and how we plan to follow the implementation of the new requirements as the project unfolds.

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Keywords: E-LAND, Privacy Risk, Cybersecurity, Project Risk, Product Reliability, Risk management.

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